

Cross-Domain Analysis of a Confidence-Calibrated Adaptive Learning Engine

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Abstract. When a single adaptive engine serves 22 apps across four certification domains, which domains concentrate misconceptions on hard items, and can this be predicted without learner data? Across 35,250 production items, score-level differentiation ($4.5\times$ misconception ratio, $d \geq 1.99$) is domain-invariant by design, but item-level concentration depends on a two-factor interaction between difficulty spread (σ) and base accuracy (b_d). When domains share $b_d=0.72$, wider σ drives 69% more hard-item misconceptions; when σ is nearly matched, a one-point b_d difference shifts the ordering. A predictor $P(d_i > 0.6) \times (1 - b_d)$ ranks all four domains correctly across a $6\times$ sensitivity sweep, enabling domain-aware scheduling from item bank statistics alone.

Keywords: Adaptive learning · Confidence calibration · Item difficulty · Educational data mining

1 Introduction

Adaptive learning engines that use identical parameters across domains produce domain-invariant score-level behavior by construction. The open question is which *item bank properties* modulate item-level behavior, and whether the modulation is predictable from observable metadata [11,8]. Item difficulty has been studied through IRT [5], incorporated into knowledge tracing [9], and modeled through Elo-based systems [10]; domain adaptation has been explored via transfer learning [3]. Yet how difficulty distributions interact with confidence-calibrated adaptation across domains is unexplored.

We analyze a production confidence-calibrated engine deployed across four professional certification domains (22 apps, 35,250+ items) using per-item difficulty and Bloom’s tier data [1]: **RQ1:** How do difficulty spread and domain base accuracy interact to drive item-level misconception concentration? **RQ2:** Can this interaction be predicted from item bank statistics alone, and what scheduling opportunities does it identify?

2 System and Domains

The engine processes binary confidence judgments through six cascaded algorithms including asymmetric scoring (+3/−5), misconception detection (high-

Table 1. Domain characteristics from production item banks (35,250 items, 22 apps). Key parameters: difficulty σ and base accuracy b_d .

Characteristic	Beauty	Health.	Prof.	IT
Applications	4	4	4	10
Total MC items	5,950	7,000	7,800	14,500
Difficulty σ	.119	.146	.156	.148
Base accuracy b_d	.72	.71	.65	.72

confidence errors), and Bloom’s-aligned assessment [1,4]. It is deployed in 22 production apps across four brand families with privacy-preserving on-device storage and fully offline operation: learners study without internet access (e.g., during long-haul travel or in areas with limited connectivity), so no server-side telemetry exists. Table 1 summarizes item bank characteristics.

Each domain aggregates 4–10 separately authored apps: Beauty (cosmetology, esthetics, barbering, nail tech), Healthcare (pharmacy, nursing, medical assisting), Professional (military aptitude, insurance, cannabis, project management), and IT (10 apps across CompTIA, AWS, SnowPro, ITIL). Difficulty and Bloom’s tier were assigned by domain subject-matter experts during content authoring. Statistics reflect structural field properties, not any single author’s choices.

3 Cross-Domain Simulation

We extend [1] with per-item data from production databases. Item difficulty modulates accuracy: $a = b_d + m_l - \lambda(d_i - 0.5)$, where b_d is domain base accuracy (Table 1), $m_l \in [0.00, 0.15]$ is mastery bonus (accumulated through correct responses), and λ is difficulty sensitivity (default 0.15). Each b_d is informed by published first-attempt pass rates for the domain’s constituent exams (e.g., PTCB $\approx 70\%$, CNA $\approx 78\%$, CompTIA $\approx 72\%$, insurance licensing $\approx 60\%$); the offline-first architecture precludes estimation from learner data. Bloom’s tier modulates confidence-when-correct (+0.05 at T1 to -0.10 at T6) [6].

Two profiles drive the core analysis: well-calibrated (WC: $c_+ = 0.9$, $c_- = 0.2$) and overconfident (OC: 0.9, 0.9), totaling 8,000 runs (2 profiles \times 4 domains \times 1,000 seeds; 30 days, 20 items/session). Sensitivity sweeps vary $\lambda \in [0.05, 0.30]$ and b_d (± 0.02) across 200 seeds per condition.

4 Results

RQ1: A two-factor interaction drives misconception concentration. Difficulty σ ranges from 0.119 to 0.156 and b_d from 0.65 to 0.72 across 35,250 items (Table 1); these two properties jointly predict item-level behavior (Table 2). Score-level metrics confirm the engine works as designed: WC profiles achieve $d \geq 1.99$ and OC profiles generate $\approx 4.5\times$ more total misconception flags across

Table 2. Simulation results (mean \pm SD, 1,000 seeds). CS = confidence score, MF = misconception flags, **HM** = hard-item ($d_i > 0.6$) misconceptions. WC Cohen’s $d \geq 1.99$ across all domains.

Domain	Type	CS	MF	HM
Beauty	WC	66.8 \pm 2.2	38 \pm 6	4 \pm 3
	OC	56.4 \pm 3.0	171 \pm 12	19 \pm 9
Health.	WC	65.8 \pm 2.3	40 \pm 6	7 \pm 4
	OC	54.8 \pm 3.0	179 \pm 13	32 \pm 13
Prof.	WC	59.2 \pm 2.4	49 \pm 7	10 \pm 5
	OC	45.6 \pm 3.2	216 \pm 13	46 \pm 17
IT	WC	67.0 \pm 2.3	39 \pm 6	7 \pm 4
	OC	56.5 \pm 3.0	171 \pm 12	32 \pm 12

all domains [1]. Item-level concentration, however, depends on both σ and b_d , consistent with the hard-easy effect in calibration research, where harder items produce greater miscalibration [7].

Three comparisons isolate the factors. *Beauty vs. IT* share $b_d=0.72$, isolating the σ effect: IT’s wider σ (0.148 vs. 0.119) yields 69% more OC hard-item misconceptions (32 vs. 19). *Healthcare vs. IT* have nearly identical σ (0.146 vs. 0.148) but Healthcare’s lower b_d (0.71 vs. 0.72) produces a small HM difference (32.2 vs. 31.6; the gap widens to 40 vs. 36 at $\lambda=0.30$), consistent with b_d exerting a secondary influence when σ is held constant. *Professional* ($b_d=0.65$) generates the most HM (**46**); its 7-point b_d gap amplifies the σ effect far beyond what spread alone predicts.

The full ordering—Professional (**46**) > Healthcare (**32**) > IT (32) > Beauty (19)—matches the analytic predictor $P(d_i > 0.6) \times (1 - b_d)$: Professional (0.060) > Healthcare (0.042) > IT (0.041) > Beauty (0.025). Neither factor alone produces this ranking: σ alone orders Professional > IT > Healthcare > Beauty, and $(1 - b_d)$ alone cannot separate three domains that share $b_d \geq 0.71$.

RQ2: Prediction and screening. The ordering holds across all $\lambda \in [0.05, 0.30]$ (Professional OC HM: 40–56) and under b_d perturbation (± 0.02). Healthcare exceeds IT when its $b_d \leq 0.73$; above that, positions converge. The predictor separates Professional (0.060) from Healthcare/IT (0.042/0.041) and Beauty (0.025). This enables difficulty-aware scheduling from item bank metadata, necessary for offline-first systems without server-side telemetry. For example, Professional’s high predictor (0.060) suggests front-loading hard items for overconfident learners, while Beauty’s low value (0.025) permits more uniform item distribution.

5 Contributions and Future Work

This analysis of 35,250 items across 22 apps contributes: (1) empirical difficulty characterization across four domains with 4–10 apps each; (2) a predictor $P(d_i > 0.6) \times (1 - b_d)$ that ranks misconception concentration from item bank

statistics alone, confirmed across a $6\times$ parameter sweep; and (3) complementary comparisons establishing that neither σ nor b_d alone explains the ordering [2]. The predictor approximates the simulation’s first-order behavior; its value is practical—cold-start domain screening from metadata alone, before any learner interaction. Score-level results ($d \geq 1.99$, $\approx 4.5\times$ ratio) are designed-in. The offline-first architecture precludes server-side telemetry, making item-bank-only methods a necessity. Future work includes opt-in validation against observed misconception concentration.

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